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Carbon Dot/Polypyrrole Nanoparticle Complexes as Multifunctional Theranostic Agents

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Characterization of Complexes for Bioimaging and Photothermal Therapy

Fig 1. (a) TEM image of the G-CDs. Inset : size distribution of G-CDs. (b) TEM image of the PPy-NPs. (c) TEM image of the G-CD/PPy-NPs.

Fig 2. (a) UV-vis absorption spectrum of the G-CDs, PPy-NPs and G-CD/PPy-NPs in the aqueous solution. (b) Fluorescence spectra of the G-CDs aqueous dispersion under different excitation wavelengths. (c) Fluorescence spectra of the G-CDs and G-CD/PPy-NPs ($\lambda_{ex} = 380$ nm).

Photothermal Property and Cell Viability

Fig 3. Photothermal properties of D.W., PPy-NPs and G-CD/PPy-NPs. (a) Temperature elevation of D.W. and G-CD/PPy-NPs under a 808 nm laser (1 W cm⁻¹). (b) The temperature change curves of G-CD/PPy-NPs (0.5 mg/mL) during five cycles. (c) Plot of cooling time versus the negative natural logarithm and the corresponding linear fitting curve.

Fig 4. Cell viability of HeLa cells treated with different concentrations of G-CD/PPy-NPs by using MTT assays.